

Geographic concentration of USA IMO teams

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The IMO is an annual mathematics competition for high school students. It was first held in 1959, with 7 participating countries, and has grown to include teams from over 100 countries. In most years the competition has run for two days, on each of which the students have been given three problems to solve in 4.5 hours. These problems are challenging, requiring substantial mathematical talent and training to solve correctly.

Despite the consequent initial concerns that a United States team might “land at the bottom of the heap”, the USA has sent a team to every IMO since 1974, and has almost always performed very well. Medal winning scores at the IMO are a strong indication of elite levels of mathematical ability: While the Fields Medal is not really comparable to the Nobel Prize, it is awarded by committee for, as Yuri Manin put it, “the most daring, profound, and stimulating research done by young mathematicians”, and so is also a marker of the scientific elite. Many Fields Medal winners have participated in the IMO, and Agarwal and Gaule have computed that the conditional probability that an IMO Gold medalist will become a Fields medalist is approximately 50 times the conditional probability for a Ph.D. from a top-ten mathematics program. IMO success is similarly correlated with other indicators of membership in the professional mathematical elite, e.g., being invited to speak at the quadrennial International Congress of Mathematicians, number of publications, number of citations, etc.

Thus, IMO participation is an early step on one path into the professional mathematical elite. Since it is so early, many of the processes by which a scientific elite reproduces itself, e.g., institutional affiliation and social ties, can have only minimal effects, and more generally, whatever advantages have accumulated have done so within the broader society, only indirectly mediated by the contemporary professional

mathematical elite. Selection for the USA IMO team begins with the nation-wide American Mathematics Competitions (AMC10/12), in which about 120,000 students participated this year. Through a sequence of further, increasingly selective competitions, 6 students are chosen to represent the USA at the IMO.

Despite this generally accessible and extremely meritocratic process, however, there are noticeable inequalities in the composition of USA IMO teams. The most obvious is that among the 208 team members 1974-2023, there are only 3 girls. Cross-cultural comparison with IMO teams from other countries strongly suggests that the USA could do more to encourage and train talented girls for the IMO, and then careers in mathematics.

Our focus here is on another striking disparity, namely the over-representation of students from a handful of schools: 12 from Stuyvesant High School (New York, NY), 11 from Phillips Exeter Academy (Exeter, NH), 7 from Thomas Jefferson High School of Science and Technology (Alexandria, VA), and 6 from Montgomery Blair High School (Silver Spring, MD)---that is more than 17% of USA IMO team members over half a century, from only four high schools. Even winners of the AMC12, the first step on the way to qualifying for the USA IMO team, are concentrated in a relatively small number of schools. Ellison and Swanson provide a very detailed analysis of the AMC12 data, and find that while there are economic and demographic factors that partially explain this phenomenon (as might be expected from the geographical concentration of, for example, scientific personnel in the USA), there are also significant school effects, raising the hope that improvements in educational programs could reduce it.

A closer look reveals that 5 of the 12 Stuyvesant students were on the first four USA IMO teams.

The presence of 2 students from the Washington, DC area on the fifth (1978) IMO team prompted the Executive Director of the MAA, Alfred B. Wilcox, to comment, “We shouldn't make too much over one year's results. But New York City has long been the intellectual capital of the country. Now the Washington area is getting a high concentration of intellectual, professional families.”. So is the geographical deconcentration of science that has been noted globally in various contexts also observable in the USA IMO team over the last half-century?

To answer this question we aggregate schools at the state level: Selective public schools can draw students from across a city, and certainly some families choose the city in which they live in order to have access to good schools. At the same time, selective private boarding schools, like Phillips Exeter Academy, draw students from across the state, if not the country and the world. The state level is a compromise, and one at which population information is also (mostly) available. Then, for each year, we ask whether the number of team members from each state is likely to have arisen as a random sample from the population distribution across states. The obvious measure to answer this question is the relative entropy (Kullback-Leibler divergence). This, however, ignores geography, counting a student in New Hampshire, or one in New Mexico, as equally not from New York. A better choice is the “earth-mover's distance” (EMD), which measures how far probability (“earth”) needs to move to convert one probability distribution into another.

For a very large random sample from the geographical population distribution, the EMD would be close to 0. For the very small samples (i.e., mostly 6) defined by the IMO teams, the EMD must be large because a lot of probability must be spread out from it to obtain the state population distribution. By simulating random draws of IMO team members from the timeseries of state population distributions, we compute an ensemble of EMD timeseries with which to compare the timeseries of EMDs of the real IMO teams. The average EMD and the slope of the trend line of this timeseries are significantly larger and smaller, respectively, than the simulations. We conclude from this that there is, in fact, geographic concentration in the USA IMO

teams (since the mean distance is larger), but that it is decreasing (since the slope is negative).

While the deconcentration of the USA IMO team may be due to *changes* in the kind of individual school effects noted by Ellison and Swanson (For example, Zuming Feng coached the team 2003-2013, while teaching at Phillips Exeter Academy. During those years, 7 Phillips Exeter students qualified for the USA IMO team; only 4 have been on the team in other years.), there are other possible factors. First, a substantial number of selective public high schools, like the North Carolina School of Mathematics and Science and the Illinois Mathematics and Science Academy (from each of which two students have joined the USA IMO team), have opened during the last half century, providing geographically (and economically) broader access to high school mathematics at levels appropriate for talented students. Second, there are also increasing numbers of opportunities for students to access mathematical training outside of school: math circles have become increasingly popular in the USA since the 1990s; the Art of Problem Solving, which provides in-person and online classes, began operating in 2003; and self-study materials are more common than previously. Our results suggest that some combination of these factors, and perhaps others, is reducing the geographical inequality in the USA IMO team path into the mathematical elite.